

Science

KHADIRARISHTA: A MEDICAL REVIEW

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Abstract

In sushrut samhita chikitsa 6/19 it has been mentioned that khadira is effective in all type of kushta. Khadirarishta is a very effective Arishta in the treatment of skin diseases specially Ekakushta. It contains 5-10% of self-generated alcohol in it. It mainly contains Khadira which is potent krumighna and kandughna dravya.

Keywords: Khadirarishta; Khadira; Medical.

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1. Introduction

Ingredients

The contents of Khadirarishta are as follows

- Khadira – Acacia catechu, Devdaru- Cedrus deodara
- Bakuchi- Psoralea corylifolia, Daruharidra- Berberis aristata
- Haritaki- Terminalia chebula, Bibhitaka- Terminalia bellerica, Amalaki- Emblica officinalis

Prakshepa Dravyas

- Dhataki- woodfordia fruticosa, Kankola – Piper cubeba, Nagakeshar – Mesua ferrea
- Jatiphala – Myristica fragrance, Lavanga – Syzygium aromaticum
- Ela – Elettaria cardamom, Tvak & Twakpatra – Cinamonum zeylonica.
- Pippali – Piper longum

Other Dravyas

- Madhu – Honey
- Sharkara – Crystallized sugar lumps, Water

Characteristics of ingredients of Khadirarishta

Dravya	Rasa	Vipaka	Virya	Doshagnata	Rogagnata
Khadira	Tikta, kashaya	Katu	Sheeta	Kapha pitta shamaka	Kushtaghna, krumighna, kasaghna, vranaropan
Devdaru	Tikta, katu, kashaya	Katu	Ushna	Kapha- vata shamaka	Kushtaghna, krumighna, dushta vana shodhana
Bakuchi	Katu, tikta	Katu	Ushna	Vata-kapha shamaka	Krumighna, kandughna, jwaraghna, swedajanana
Daruharidra	Kashaya, tikta	Katu	Ushna	Pitta-kapha shamaka	Shotaghna, vedanasthpan, vranashodhan-ropan, chakshushya
Haritaki	Pahncharasat maka Lavana varjya	Madhur	Ushna	Tridosahara	Hrudya, kushtaghna, jwaraghna, twachya, krumighna
Bubhitaka	Kashaya	Madhur	Ushna	Pitta-kaphas hamaka	Jwarahara, kasahara, virechanopaga
Amalaki	Pancharasatm aka Lavana varjya	Madhur	Sheeta	Tridoshaghna	Dahashamana, keshya, twachya

Medical Properties

- 1) Primary
 - Aam Pachaka
 - Antipruritics
 - Anthelmintic
 - Anti allergic
 - Digestive stimulants
 - Anti microbial
- 2) Secondary
 - Anti-gout
 - Anti histaminic
 - Anti inflammatory
 - Anti oxidant
 - Hepato protective

Indications

Mainly used in symptoms like Itching, Rashes and sensitive skin.

Primary Uses

1. Acne /pimples
2. Atopic dermatitis (Eczema)
3. Intestinal worms
4. Psoriasis
5. Skin allergies
6. Swollen lymph nodes
7. Urticaria

Other Uses

Spleen enlargement, liver disorders, anemia (generally due to worm infestation), tumors and cysts under the skin, heart diseases, cough and breathing troubles.

Dose

10-20 ml with luke-warm water.

Previous Work Done

1) Khadira

A. Pharmacological Study

- It has antioxidant property(V.Gayatri Devi, Anitha John,R.Sreekala Devi,A. Prabhakaran)
- Khadira is Anti-bacterial agent (Kushtaghna). It has Anti mycotic, Anti diarrhoeal properties. (Rohit kumar.khatik, Anita Sharma 2014).
- It has anti-fungal activity against dermatophytes. (thilaga Thendral, T.Laxmi 2017).

B. Clinical Study

- Acacia catechu is used in conjunctivitis, Haemoptysis, Pruritis, Leprosy, eukoderma, Skin diseases, Nausea, diarrhoea. (Kinnari Dhruve, C.R. Harisha,P.K.Prajapata oct-dec 2011)

2) Deodaru- It has Anti inflammatory, Diuretics, Anti pyretic and anti leprotic properties.

3) Bakuchi- It is used as Anti microbial, Anti bacterial, Anti fungal, Anti inflammatory.

4) Daruharidra- It is used as Rejuvenating effect. Also it is Anti pyretic, Anti pruritic, Anti haemorrhoidal properties.

5) Haritaki- It is used as Anti oxidant, Anti microbial, Anti diabetic, Hepato-protective, Anti inflammatory, Anti arthritis, Gastro intestinal and motility wound healing action.

6) Bibhitaki- It has Anti oxidant, Anti microbial, Anti diarrheal, Anti cancer, Anti diabetic, anti hypertensive, Hepato protective Action.

- 7) Amalaki- It has hepato toxic and Anti tumour properties. It is used chronic stress and Hypo lipidemia.

Side Effects

Common side effect like burning sensation or heart burn occurs when taken without water.

References

- [1] Bhaishajya Ratnawali 54/365-370.
[2] Sharangadhara samhita madhyam khanda 10/60-65.

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